

Impacts of Integrated Marketing Communications on Campaign against Hiv/Aids Pandemic in Enugu State

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Abstract:

HIV/AIDS has remained the biggest global health concern for the past two decades. There has not been any known weapon considered potent that was spared in confronting this menace, yet successfully it resisted them all, wreaking havoc relentlessly against humanity. This study which focused on Evaluating the Effects of Marketing Communication Campaign Against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State, is designed to review the quality of the marketing communication tools/strategies adopted in the HIV/AIDS programmes in the state, identify areas of weaknesses, and offer appropriate recommendations that will not only increase people's awareness of the disease, but will also avert the enormous human and maternal mortality claimed by the epidemic in the state on daily basis. Enugu State was chosen for this study because according to the sentinel survey of 2005, the state has the highest HIV/AIDS prevalence of 6.5% in the entire South East geopolitical zone. This study adopted the survey method of research design, using the instruments of questionnaire and personal interviews as data generating tools. Data for the study which were tested and analysed, using correlation statistical tool, were collected by distributing questionnaire to three hundred and fifty four (354) respondents selected across the state. Four (4) hypotheses were formulated to test: (i) if there is any significant relationship between increased television messages and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu state. (ii) if there is any significant relationship between increased radio messages and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state, (iii) if there is any significant relationship between increased newspaper messages and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state, (iv) if there is any significant relationship between increased word-of-mouth and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state. The findings were that there are significant relationships between increased messages from each of these tools: television, radio, newspapers, the word-of-mouth, and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state. In view of the above findings, however, we recommended that the tools be properly and adequately exploited in creating the necessary awareness campaign against the scourge in the state. Also recommended is the full mobilization and involvement of the HIV/AIDS support groups, the musicians/film-makers, and the gate-keepers in the state in delivering these messages safely and conveniently to the different segments of the target audience whom they are meant for, especially those in the rural communities.

Keywords: HIV, AIDS, Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC), Advertising, Public Relations and Sales Promotion.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The first case of HIV/AIDS was reported in 1980 in the US (Dauda, 2012). It is the most deadly disease and had since remained incurable till this very moment (Ikemike, 2015). In the past two decades, the HIV/AIDS pandemic has remained the biggest global health concern that heralded the 21st century. The attention commanded by this epidemic assumes top priority in the policy agenda of the world leaders which has translated into series of declarations and financial commitments targeted at stamping out the scourge. It has apparently defiled the arsenals of the world's famous scientists and non-scientists alike. In spite of the unprecedented efforts made in stopping the epidemic, it has not relented but kept spreading across the globe, with an excruciating grip of terror against humanity like an uncompromising monster. The disease has, no doubt, devastated the most productive, reproductive and economically dependable segment of the human

population, a group whose survival constitutes about 80 percent of work population. But who is this most dreaded monster capable of unleashing such mayhem to the basic fundamental values of the society by crippling the world's human capacity and devastating its economy? One may ask.

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) is the pathogenic organism (virus) that causes AIDS. This virus is found in the body fluids (particularly blood, semen, and vaginal secretions) of infected persons. It is a retrovirus that damages function of the cells of the immune system (Awoleye and Thron, 2015). The HIV/AIDS virus infection has been on the increase since its first case in 1992. In 1999, between 5.1%-5.4% had been infected (Fawole, Ogunkan and Adegoke, 2011). The impact of HIV/AIDS has a ripple effect. A study by Danjuma and Bashir (2013) revealed that HIV/AIDS affect not only the body of the victim, but also their savings and standard of living too. It is believed that most (possibly all) people infected with HIV, develop AIDS. **Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS)** is a secondary immune deficiency state characterized by progressive damage to the body's immune system which results in the development of a number of opportunistic fatal infections. AIDS is not a disease in itself but a condition that occurs when one's body's immune system can no longer protect itself from diseases. HIV/AIDS is not curable. All efforts made by scientists all over the world in search of a possible solution to this singular global plague have failed woefully. It had been destroying many lives in both local communities and urban areas the world over (Ojo, Agara, and Pojwan, 2015). Most victims fail to visit the clinics for free tests and even when tested positive, fail to go for antiretroviral drugs because of the stigmatization and discrimination (Ojjeabu, Eze, Fashola, Bello and Arute, 2014). But nonetheless, the condition is preventable though. Besides, it is not like the other past epidemics such as cholera, measles, small/chicken poxes, etc whose transmission was by air, water or other forms of physiological contacts with the carrier. It is also not transmitted by any kind of insects like in the case of mosquitoes and malaria. However, HIV/AIDS can be transmitted through the following sources:

- (a) Unprotected sexual contact with an infected person.
- (b) The use of contaminated and unsterilized sharp instruments.
- (c) An infected mother to her infant during pregnancy, delivery or breastfeeding,
- (d) Blood transfusion.

Statement of the Problem

There had been media messages in the fight against HIV/AIDS but not much had been done in ascertaining the extent these messages could foster a change in behavior by people (Maxwell, 1995). The war against HIV/AIDS is a global project which had continually pulled together various nations of different backgrounds and ideologies to chart a possible common and decisive course for confronting the scourge. The results of these deliberations had manifested in the form of resolutions and declarations in which Nigeria had often been signatory to and consequently domesticated for use. Subsequently, the Federal government of Nigeria had devoted reasonable parts of her budgetary allocations, on annual basis, to wage this battle since the disease was first diagnosed in the country. She has established the National Action Committee on AIDS (NACA) with the responsibility to articulating comprehensive programmes to prevent; control and contain the HIV/AIDS infection in Nigeria.

This effort was further extended down to the states, Local Government Areas and the community levels through the formation of the States Action Committees on AIDS (SACAS), Local Government Action Committees on AIDS (LACA), and the Community Based Organisations (CBOS). The impacts of the various Donor Agencies and the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) had been most rewarding in this regard too. Most of these commitments had been channeled in the areas of designing and executing various campaign programmes towards mitigating the rapid spread of this scourge. But in spite all these efforts, the prevalence rate of the disease in the state remained high with increasing daily reports of new cases. This is because the appropriate marketing communication tools such as television, radio, newspapers, and the word-of-mouth, have not been fully exploited in creating effective awareness campaign against the disease in the state. Consequently, this

study hopes to ascertain the effects of increased mobilization/application of these tools in this campaign project so that necessary recommendations that will affect the desired change can be made.

While many researches had been done on HIV/AIDS, no emphasis had been made on the adoption of integrated marketing communications, especially the heightened bombardment by the radio, television, newspaper and magazine to educate the masses about HIV/AIDS pandemic in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effects of Marketing Communication Campaigns against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are:

1. To determine the extent increased television messages can create awareness campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State.
2. To investigate the effects of increased radio messages on awareness campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state.
3. To find out the effects of increased newspaper messages in creating awareness campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state.
4. To ascertain the effects of increased use of the word-of-mouth in creating awareness campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state.

Hypothesis

In order to achieve the above stated objectives, the following four (4) null hypotheses were formulated and tested in this study.

1. There is no significant relationship between increased television messages and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State.
2. There is no significant relationship between increased radio messages and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state.
3. There is no significant relationship between increased newspaper messages and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state.
4. There is no significant relationship between increased use of the word-of-mouth and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state.

Review of Related Literature

A Review of the Marketing Communication Strategies Already Adopted in the State HIV/AIDS Campaign Programme

Also reviewed by this team were the following key marketing communication strategies and techniques so far adopted in the state HIV/AIDS intervention programmes.

Charts: Charts are similar to posters in many ways, but differ from them in that they exhibit summarized information or data in graphics or tabular forms or by use of symbols, pictures or figures (Nwosu, 1996). They are very important communication tools usually used for references or as supplementary information lectures, talks in workshops or seminars, like in the HIV/AIDS campaign.

Stickers and Banners: Like in posters, stickers and banners make use of words, pictures, colours, images and are pasted in locations where they can be easily seen by passers-by. Banners and stickers carry such anti HIV/AIDS messages that inform and educate the public such as *“spread the message and not the virus”*, *“AIDS no dey show for face,”* *“with condom, I dey kampe,”* etc. In fact they have proved to be very valuable media material for the gospel against HIV/AIDS both in the state, the country and the entire world.

Billboards: Billboards are usually amplified or over-enlarged versions of most posters, bearing the same messages or fewer messages (Kotler, 1997). They are usually placed in strategic places in the cities for people passing in their vehicles to read at a glance. They are usually employed as “reinforcement” or message reminders” to the mass public.

Dramas/Cartoons: These are very effective public relations tools dispersed to the public through both print and electronic media both in English language and local vernacular. They usually carry warning messages against such vices or behaviours targeted at like in the case of HIV/AIDS scourge. Dramas are also often times shown live on stage in schools, churches, village squares, etc.

Pamphlets/Brochures/Handbills (leaflets): These are very useful communication tools employed in spreading short messages to the target audiences that are usually literate. In fact the campaign against HIV/AIDS have been able to penetrate thousands of people in Enugu State, the entire country, and the world at large through the use of pamphlets, brochures and handbills. Millions of such pamphlets containing specific, concise and clear information on AIDS are distributed to various people both as individuals and organizations. In fact everywhere people gather, in churches, schools, market places, even to travelers at the motor parks, airports, youth organizations, social clubs and in hotels, handbills are used to reach them.

Books: Books are one of the strongest medium of communication in public relations programmes. Many good books have been written and published on HIV/AIDS in Nigeria, while a good number are shipped into the country by the United Nation’s agencies and other international non-governmental organizations. More of such good books that reveal the ill-effects of HIV/AIDS on the individuals, families and the societies, offering empirical (statistical) evidences, should be readily and freely available to all the literate persons in the society especially our students in the institutions of higher learning.

Journals/Magazines: These are very powerful communication tools that could be employed for institutional/organizational campaigns against the spread of HIV/AIDS. Such publication could be either for internal or external publics. A good example of such magazine is the very one published by the Emenite Plc, Emene, Enugu. Though it is targeted at the employees of the company, but it has been so valuable to everybody who had been opportuned to come across a copy.

Features, Articles, Editorials, and News Analysis/ Commentaries: Messages could also be sent across to the target publics through the above mentioned media techniques. However, they require the ability of a communication expert who is gifted in writing skill, or in the words of Nwosu, (1996), “someone who is sharp on the pen”. This means that he must be educated, serious minded, articulate and well-focused. Having discovered that the use of these tools (techniques) in the fight against HIV/AIDS spread in the state was not actually yielding the required results as more new cases were recorded on daily basis while many patients were still not willing to declare their status due to the stigma associated with the disease, it therefore became more imperative that more subtle approaches are needed in order to achieve a better result.

Marketing Communications Strategies not Adopted in the State HIV/AIDS Campaign Programmes

Counselling: Health and social workers are mobilized in schools to provide special counseling sections for students. Counseling is a face to face communication media which allows the participants or recipients to ask vital questions in any area or issue they are not clear about which will facilitate their making an informed and rational decisions.

Press Briefings/Conferences: These could be used in public relations campaigns to inform the target publics the dangers of HIV/AIDS. Press Conference is a forum arranged to release or break “worthwhile news” to the press and usually offers an opportunity for the journalists to ask some questions on the issue(s) at hand and receive answers to them. Media-briefings are used to provide further information on existing matters of importance (Black, 1989).

Interviews/Phone-in Programmes: These programmes are presented through the print and electronic media like Radios, Televisions, Newspapers and Magazines where professionals like the health professionals are granted interviews in the paper or featured to receive and answer questions from the public's especially in the case of phone-in-programmes on the burning issues like the HIV/AIDS. These are often aired on the ESBS Radio and TV stations, NTA media chat, FRCN's "Radio-Link", "Media-Link", "Ka oha mara" etc.

Documentary Films: Documentaries, according to Epele (1976), are very important communication media for reaching out to both selected and or mass publics in public relations campaigns. A list of such documentaries on HIV/AIDS is produced and aired both on our local, national and international television channels today. Such tools are very important and quite result oriented because they combine the effects of sight, sound, colour, drama, etc in delivering messages. Nothing could be more touching and result-oriented to the viewer than to see AIDS patients on such firms.

Opinion Leaders: The enlistment of credible opinion leaders is one of the most effective strategies in this crusade which needs to be exploited more in HIV/AIDS campaigns especially in our rural areas. The skill entails using opinion leaders' authorities with considerable influences to effect the needed changes in the decisions and actions of their community members. Such people include the traditional rulers, town union leaders, teachers and head teachers of schools, local priests/pastors, women leaders, youth leaders, etc. A motor park tout for instance, who commands the cars, the respect and support of his colleagues, is an opinion leader in that park and could be used to effectively sell the message(s) inside such motor park.

Suggestion Boxes: Communication is said not to be complete without a feedback (Black, 1989). One of such feedback mechanisms usually employed in marketing communication programmes is the use of suggestion boxes normally placed in strategic places for the target publics. This is to enable them air their views freely, conveniently and confidentially. This technique is also very effective in programme monitoring, evaluation and re-strategizing or re-planning activities.

Exhibitions: "Exhibition promotes/reinforces face to face communication as "seeing is believing" makes impression more convincing" (Jefkins, 1982). The impact of exhibition in such practical and "life and death" matters like HIV/AIDS cannot be over emphasized. This, as a matter of fact, is a form of using documentary film to deliver the message. In fact, by this strategy, many peoples' lives have been saved. They have been adequately informed and sensitized about HIV/AIDS and subsequently have been able to take positive and informed measures of preventing and controlling the spread of the virus.

Enugu State Strategic Plan (ESSP) on HIV/AIDS

Generally, the observed gaps from the review exercise (survey) was so glaring that the development of State Strategic Plan (SSP) 2006-2010 became imminent. The ESSP was initiated by the SNR and UNDP thereby setting the stage for strategic and operational planning, policy review, development and resource mobilization necessary for the programme. The development of the plan was a major achievement of the state government as an effective tool for the coordination of the HIV/AIDS response in the state. The plan was a people-owned document which seeks to expand and galvanize resource mobilization efforts, and ensure comprehensive buy-in by stakeholders and development partners whose contributions have been a major milestone in the achievements so far recorded in the project, both in the State and the entire country.

The Enugu State HIV/AIDS Strategic Plan (ESSP) is a Strategic Framework designed to guide the implementation of an expanded and comprehensive response to HIV/AIDS epidemic for five year period in Enugu State between 2006 and 2010. The plan serves as a HIV/AIDS policy document for the state, and as a veritable resource mobilization tool, that is expected to streamline and harmonize the entire resource in-flow and location, as well as yearly programme design, forecasts, and implementation. Richly detailed in content, the plan has taken into consideration the stages of the epidemic, the level and adequacy of the response, the absorptive capacity of systems, and available infrastructure. Particularly, it identified different interventions

and strategies to address the issues. The ESSP is the product of a broadly participatory and consultative process designed to bring together government agencies, development partners, faith based organizations, civil society organisations and the private sector. ENSACA initially had a board membership of nine (9) persons, and later was increased to twenty six (26) persons to accommodate the expanded stakeholders' interest. The key constituents of the board include the following:

- (i) The government agencies which comprised of ENSACA, and some line ministries.
- (ii) The Civil Society Organisations (CSOs)
- (iii) The International Development Partners and the NGOs,
- (iv) The Local Non-governmental Organisations
- (v) The Faith Based Organisations (FBOs)
- (vi) The Private Sector Organisations,
- (vii) The Academia, and
- (viii) The Women and Youths Organisations
- (ix) Hospital Representatives

The Role of the Non-Governmental Agencies in the State HIV/AIDS Intervention Programmes

Whenever the intervention efforts made by various interest groups on HIV/AIDS programmes in Enugu State is being discussed, one must not fail to mention and appreciate the immense contributions made by the various non-governmental organisations (local and international) who had, in various manners, partnered with the federal and state governments in this all important assignment. Below are the summarized accounts of their individual activities towards eradicating the scourge in the state.

Coalitions and Networks of Civil Society Organisations

Civil society is made up of all associations and networks that operate between the family and the state in which membership and activities are voluntary. Records have it that in all social and economic situations, the best results are achieved where the three sectors of the society: private, public and civil work together by playing complimentary roles in common policy formulation and implementation. Among the civil society networks whose efforts impacted very positively and prominently in the HIV/AIDS programmes in Enugu State are the following:

- (i) Civil Society Networks on HIV/AIDS in Nigeria (CISNHAN)
- (ii) Civil Society Consultative Group on HIV/AIDS in Nigeria (CISCGHAN)
- (iii) Network of People with HIV/AIDS in Nigeria (NEPWHAN): A coalition of about thirty (30) support groups formally known as 'Coalition of Enugu State Support Groups Organisation (CESSGO).'
- (iv) National Network on Reproductive Health (NINPREH)
- (v) Health and Women Network (HERWIN)
- (vi) Global Health and Awareness Research Foundation (GHARF)
- (vii) The Red Cross Society of Nigeria
- (viii) National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW)
- (ix) Christian Health Organisation of Nigeria (CHAN), etc.

The Civil Society Organisations in the state have no doubt, contributed very positively to the HIV/AIDS response in the state in different manners. With their advocacy capacity initiatives, they have been able to achieve a great success in the areas of eradication of widowhood and harmful traditional practices identified as major contributory factor in the establishment of new infections in the state. They have also contributed immensely to the passage of bills on various obnoxious practices that affect the PLWHA and other vulnerable groups in the society. They have been able to record these achievements by channeling efforts in strengthening capacity of the political leaders, decision makers and other influentials on HIV/AIDS policies, stigmatization of PLWHA, legal rights, human rights and many gender related issues in the state. They have equally organized,

and implemented many awareness and sensitization activities in collaboration with the Ministry of Women Affairs and National Orientation Agency (NOA), to redress violence against women in the state.

Foreign Partner Agencies

The policy environment for HIV/AIDS in Nigeria is noted for its multiplicity of actors with different motivations and impacts on the policy process and implementation. The international development partners and the donor agencies constitute a very important group/actors in the HIV/AIDS policy process in Enugu State and indeed, in the entire country. This group has not only initiated the policies, they have also funded and even taken the lead in the implementation processes of the entire programmes. At the national level, these agencies have played a major role in advocacy and dialoguing with the federal government to ensure the formulation of the national AIDS policy and development of the HEAP document. They also have been involved in funding and setting programme priorities through supporting intervention programmes/projects and capacity building through technical assistance and training.

Communication Definitions

Communication, according to the communication expert, Nwosu (2001), is a process of information, ideas and opinions exchange within, between or among individuals, groups, organizations or nations (usually made up of human beings) in a social or societal context. It is simply the process of sending and receiving messages from one to another (Al-Sadeghi, Alsaqa and Fadel, 2009). According to Onyebuagu (1997) communication means imparting of thoughts, opinions, ideas or information, by speech, writing, signs, gesticulations, movements and or silence, from one individual to another, etc. "Communication is a two way process of transmitting or exchanging information (facts, thoughts, opinions or feelings) through speech, signs or action, between a source and a receiver" (FMH, 2004). Another school of thought defined communication as "a two-way process whereby a person or group of persons (sender) pass a message through a channel to another person or group (receiver) and get(s) a feedback which acknowledges that the recipient(s) understand(s) the message" (Smith,1993). Communication involves a relationship brought about by sharing of ideas or establishment of commonness of ideas in line with the two latin words that form the root of the concept of communication, "communicare" which means, to share or establish commonness, and "communis" which means "common" (Nwosu, 2001). Through communication, knowledge, values, and social norms are shared. When people communicate, the intention of the initiator of the communication could be to pass on information, request action or just relate with the person or group with whom s/he is communicating.

However, it is important to note that not all communication meets the needs of the initiator or the recipient of the communication. When this happens, we say that the communication is ineffective. Effective communication results by following closely a road map that seeks to reduce uncertainty and ensure that both the initiator and recipient understand one another. However, it is difficult to imagine a situation where communication is so perfect that there is no uncertainty at all. This is because perfect communication is difficult to achieve.

Types of Communication

While some authors classify communication into four major types or forms namely: intrapersonal, interpersonal, mass communication and organizational, others classify it into three main types, namely, intrapersonal, interpersonal and mass communication. But there is a general belief that communication can be further classified into many more types. On this premise therefore, we classified communication as many types as possible in a manner that it will project the very picture we hope to paint. Under this very classification we have as much as ten communication types. They include:

Intrapersonal Communication: This is the communication type that involves only one person or individual. Here, the common concepts of exchange, transaction, sharing, establishment of commonness is often not

obvious. Example of this type of communication includes; soliloquy (one talking to himself), talking aloud or silently, the justification we make for our actions, etc.

Interpersonal Communication: This is person-to-person type of communication that involves two entities which may be two individuals, two groups, an individual and a group, etc. Here, there is usually an easily identifiable communicator and a receiver of the communicated message or information. This means that all parties involved, are either senders or receivers. Interpersonal communication is a person-to-person, two-way, verbal and non-verbal interaction that involves sharing of information and feelings between individuals or in small groups that establish trusting relationships. This type of communication is one of the key communication components influencing behaviour change (FMH, 2004). Interpersonal communication is influenced by the attitudes, feelings, values, social norms, and the environment of the people involved. It complements, reinforces and elaborates messages presented in the mass media, and vice-versa, (FMH, 2004).

Mass Communication: Mass communication, otherwise known as mass mediated communication, is the type that transmits messages to large audiences (masses) through the mass media, such as Television or radio.

Basic Elements of the Communication Process

The fundamental elements underlying effective communication are common in all communication situations and in most communication models. The exact number of items or terminology used may differ but are basically similar and convey the same meaning. Philip Kotler (2012) offered a communication model with eight elements. Two of the elements represent the major **parties** in a communication – **sender** and **receiver**. Two represent the major **tools** – **message** and **media**. Four represent the major **functions** – **encoding, decoding, response** and **feedback**. The last element in the system is **noise** (random and competing messages that may interfere with the intended communication).

Figure 2.1 Elements in the communication Process – Kotler (2012)

According to Nwosu (2001) these key elements include-

SOURCE: The source otherwise called the **Sender** is the originator of the message. It could be an individual or an organization. The receiver may or may not know the source’s identity. This does not change anything. The source is not always recognized. Most often the medium like radio, newspapers, etc, which serve as the channel of transmission or even the presenter of such messages, are mistaken to mean the source. The source (sender) is the identified individuals or organizations who sponsored such programmes/messages. To ensure more effectiveness here, the *Sender* must:

- know the subject well
- Be interested in the subject
- Have decided on an objective
- Know the receiver/Audience and establish rapport with them.
- Speak/design the message at the level of the receiver/ audience

- Choose an appropriate channel

MESSAGE: The message which originated from the source is an idea in transmittable form – whose content is suggested or determined by the circumstances that gave rise to the idea in the first place. In every situation therefore, the communication experts must determine the appropriate idea to communicate and be as certain as possible that the message is right for the purpose and for the right audience. This is why proper analysis of the individual and groups who made up the target audience is very important because it puts the planner in a better position to understand what the communication objectives must be and what ideas should be communicated to produce the desired effect. It is the articulated content that is put into communicable form (encoded) into a message. To ensure effective communication, the message must be:

- Clear and concise
- Accurate
- Relevant to the needs of the receiver (meaningful)
- Timely
- Applicable to the situation

ENCODING: Encoding is the process of putting the message into a form that can be transmitted, received, and understood by the receiver (Onyebuagu, 1997). This is achieved when the originator of the idea tries to recreate in the receiver's mind precisely the same thing he has in mind. This requires using mutually understood signs and symbols to put the senders' message together in a form that will be understood by the receiver or audience (Nwosu, 2001). In other words, when we communicate, we are trying to establish "commonness" with someone, even though we know that this is difficult to establish. This therefore means that the devices used in the encoding process must mean the same thing to both the source and the receiver; otherwise communication will not have taken place. Words must be very carefully chosen in the encoding process so that they have the same general meaning for source and receiver. A strategic way to achieve result here is by stratifying/segmenting the audience (market) into homogeneous groups and then communicating to each group as if the people in the group were one receiver. Kotler (2012) captured this well when he stated that "for a message to be effective, the sender's encoding process must mesh with the receiver's decoding process. The more the sender's field of experience overlaps with that of the receiver, the more effective the message is likely to be". It is worthy to note here that even though the source is always the originator of the message, he is not always the encoder. This is because there are certain situations he is not qualified to encode the message on a form that would be accepted and understood by the receiver. Organisations such as advertising agencies, media personnel, public relations agencies, etc often act as professional encoders of messages.

CHANNELS: The channel, also known as the medium that serves as the link between the source and the receiver, is the means by which the message is transmitted. This could be in the form of human voice, like in personal selling situations, it could be in printed words like in the magazines and newspapers and advertising; it could be voices on the radios or television; it could also be a combination of these and others. To ensure more effectiveness here, the *channel* must be:

- Appropriate
- Accessible
- Affordable
- Appealing

NOISE: Noise is any distraction or distortion of the reception and understanding of the message. Onyebuagu (1997). The distraction may be some kind of activity or condition that affects the encoding, the reception or the understanding of the message. It is activity aroused noise or outside noise when it is coming from the physical environment. But some can be caused by certain conditions within the source or the receiver. Such conditions include illness, preoccupation, anger, worry, uneasiness, discomfort, etc. There are two dimensions to noise in

communication: **semantic noise** and **channel noise**. Semantic noise refers to any distortion in the communicated message arising from the meaning of the words or symbols used in encoding the message. Channel noise include the snow on our television screens and the ink-smear, misprints, missing paragraphs or pages in the newspaper or magazines that distort the message transmitted with them.

FEEDBACK: Communication is not just a process but also a two-way-process. The receiver or audience usually sends back his or their reactions of responses to the communicated message through a process known as the “feedback”, using the mutually understood code or symbol and the appropriate medium or channel available and acceptable to both him and the source or sender of the original message. Feedback refers to the clues that indicate whether or not the message is being received and the degree to which it is understood (Onyebuagu, 1997). Obtaining feedback is more obvious in face-to-face situations than in mass media where it constitutes a problem. A simple gesture could constitute a feedback in face to face situations. The clue may be nothing more than a frown, a nod of the head, a raised eyebrow or oral message. If he did not perform the feedback process, then communication has not taken place because nothing, according to Nwosu (2001), has been shared. The feedback by the receiver is usually based on whatever effects the communicated message has on him. Feedback can be immediate or delayed, positive or negative. But nonetheless, they are all useful and necessary in any communication situation (Nwosu, 2001). In summary, the Feedback:

- is what the receiver ends up doing in response to the message
- is the assessment of the message impact
- can be spontaneous, immediate or delayed.

DECODING: It is difficult to divorce the decoder from the receiver as people because the receiver is the decoder. But for purposes of clarity, ‘**decoding**’ can be expressed as an activity while **receiver** is the person who performs the activity. Decoding, which is the opposite of encoding, is a process or activity that takes place at the **receiver’s** end of the channel where he tries to reproduce the source’s idea in his mind for communication to occur. And for perfect communication to take place, the message must be decoded in precisely the same way it was encoded. This process starts as soon as the receiver becomes aware of the message. If he is able to translate the message into an idea that matches or recreates what the source had in mind, communication has taken place. Therefore, for effective communication to take place, the encoder must have to play his own part very well by ensuring that he used language, signs and symbols that not only have correct denotative meaning but also connotative meanings to the receiver consistent with the idea the source is attempting to transmit (Onyebuagu, 1997). To ensure the effectiveness of the message, the *receiver* must:

- be aware, interested and willing to accept the message
- have a reason to listen
- listen attentively
 - provide feedback

Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) Mix

The major problem confronting many business organizations today does not lie on what to produce, or how to price or channel it appropriately to the prospective consumers. It borders on how to reach the customers (present and potential) with the obvious challenges of determining what to say, to whom, how to say it and how often: - marketing communications. This is not the coercive version but the mild and persuasive type that not only guarantee the free flow of information about the organization and its products, but that which ensures a strong and lasting buyer-seller or consumer-marketer relationship. No wonder why marketing communication is defined as an interactive dialogue between the company and its customers which takes place during the pre-selling, selling, consumption and post-consumption stages, (Kotler, 2012). Effective marketing communication demands a proper application of the modern communication principles and practice to the marketing campaign packaging. This makes it incumbent on the marketer to develop the right message, select an appropriate media and accurately target the campaign to facilitate the marketing process.

Marketing Communication Mix

Schuller and Rasticuva (2011) discussed marketing communication in their study “Marketing Communications Mix of Universities - Communication With Students in an Increasing Competitive University Environment While treating the marketing communication mix, the strategically crucial fact we must always bear in mind is that all the **four Ps** known as the marketing variables have the potential to transmit messages about the organization and its offerings, not just the one labeled “Promotion”. However, promotion reminds us that the right products (or services) are not only to be made available in the right place, offered at the right price, but must also be backed with the right kind of message if they are to be successful in today’s crowded and noisy market place. Nwosu (2001) re-emphasized this point by stating that “modern marketing calls for more than developing a good product, pricing it attractively and making it accessible to the target customers, “companies must also communicate with their present and potential customers as every company is inevitably cast into the role of communicator and promoter” (Kotler, 2012).

Kotler (2012) offered what he called the five modes of marketing communication as the key functional areas of marketing communications mix as follows:

1. Advertising
2. Sales promotions
3. Public relations/publicity
4. Personal selling.
5. Direct marketing

Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) Mix

Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) can be defined as a concept under which a company carefully integrates and coordinates its many communications channels to deliver a clear, consistent, and compelling message about the organization and its products (Kotler and Armstrong, 2012; Belch and Belch, 2001). It is a synergistic approach through which a company selects and blends its marketing communications mix tools to project an arrowhead towards winning a marketing war. It is really a rifle approach as it selects and applies specific marketing promotional tools to a specific audience; avoiding the risks of wasting marketing and management resources. Integrated Marketing Communications became popular in the 90s as a veritable strategy for succeeding in any marketing programme (Mubushar, Haider and Iftikhar, 2013; Porcu, Barrio -Garcia, Kitchen, 2012; Ul-Rehman and Ibrahim, 2011). It is a marketing strategy adopted all over the world and as a consumer oriented approach to marketing instead of an organizational oriented one, it combines the promotional tools logically (Naeem, Bilal, and Naz, 2013). A proper and careful integration of all the marketing communication mix components into a definite marketing communication programme points at the direction of a modern concept of marketing communication known as Integrated Marketing Communication which Nwosu (2001) identified as “PROMOTION-PLUS”. According to him, “Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) is promotion plus other marketing and communication activities that do not necessarily fit into the standard of promotional strategies in terms of form, objectives, ideology or philosophy and practices.” It is more efficacious in handling most promotion problem as it communicates more universally, clearer and effectively (Sosidia and Telrandhe, 2010). Integrated Marketing Communication has been described as the new direction in marketing communications that applies communication strategies to modern marketing as an inevitable response to the new challenges posed for the promotional ‘P’ in the marketing process by the demands of products, service and social marketing in the recent times, (Nwosu, 2001). IMC is “a deliberate, planned and systematic attempt to contextually expand the traditional or conventional promotional strategies or activities (e.g. advertising and public relations) and integrate them with other marketing communications activities to facilitate the achievement of defined marketing objectives” (Nwosu, 2001). Management apply it to integrate and improve their marketing programmes (Reid, Luxton and Mavondo, 2005).

IMC is a combined way of communicating with consumers such that the techniques of advertising, public relations, publicity, sales promotions, etc, are used together to win a marketing success. It is non-dependent on any one particular item of the promotion mix marketing. It is very important in executing international marketing (Ehikwe, 2013). It bolsters brand equity (Mongkol, 2014). The American Association of Advertising Agencies (AAAA) described IMC as “a concept of marketing communication planning that recognizes the added value in a programme that integrates a variety of strategic disciplines e.g. general advertising, direct response, sales promotion and public relations, and combines these disciplines to provide clarity, consistency and maximum communication impact”. In all, the researcher summarized these views into a working definition of IMC thus: “the deliberate and judicious blending of the conventional promotools with the other marketing communication activities to achieve optimum promotional performance.”

Advertising and Direct Marketing

Advertising: Nwosu (2001) defines advertising as “any form of non-personal presentation and promotion of persons, institutions, ideas, goods or services by an identified sponsor, using appropriate medium or media of communication.” Advertising provides necessary and persuasive information to the buyers, both in awareness creation and in assisting them in making decisions to buy, especially while choosing among other competing brands of products. Advertising is very effective in all the stages of product life-cycle. It does not only give information on the benefits of the product, services, etc, it informs the customers when, where and how to reach the products. The major characteristics that distinguished this form of marketing communication mix from the others is the fact that the message must be paid for by an identified sponsor.

Direct Marketing: Direct marketing is modern specie of advertising defined as an interactive system of marketing which uses one or more advertising media to effect measurable response and/or transaction at any location. It is also referred to as “one-on-one customer- data-based marketing and media activities that ensure two-way communication with and direct measurable responses from existing or potential customers” (Nwosu, 2001). Direct Marketing (DM) communicates person to person but through an intervening channel, such as the post (a mailshot or mailing), door-to-door delivery (a mail drop), the telephone (telemarketing) or a fax line, guaranteeing exposure to a selected individual within a target market. For many years now, the only form of direct marketing in use was direct mail. The major direct marketing media as identified by Nwosu (2001) which are still quite new and therefore not yet popular among the developing nations of the world include the following: (i) Coupons (ii) Direct mail (iii) Customer and business magazines (iv) Catalogues (v) Newspapers (vi) Telephones (vii) Television (viii) radio, etc.

Public Relations, Publicity and Event Marketing

Public Relations:

Nwosu, (2001) observed that Public Relation is viewed among the experts in the field in two different perspectives. “leadership and management function that helps achieve organizational objectives, define philosophy, and facilitate organizational change” (Okolo, Agu, Obikeze, Ugonna and Wali, 2015). First, as strategy for overall corporate survival, and secondly, as a marketing support system or tool. As a strategy for overall corporate survival, it could be defined as “a philosophy and function of management which evaluates publications, identifies the policies of an individual or organisation with public interest and executes a programme of actions to earn public understanding and acceptance (Nwosu, 2001). In this perspective, it is further explained that public relations and marketing are seen and practiced as equal and complimentary partners in achieving the objectives of any organization, including the selling of its goods and services. As a marketing support system or tool, it is defined as “a promotional activity that aims to communicate a favourable image of the product or its marketer and to promote goodwill,” (Nwosu, 2001. Public Relations, as advanced by Harlow (1976), is “a distinctive management function which helps to establish and maintain mutual lines of communication and understanding, acceptance and cooperation between an organization and its publics”. According to Nkwocha (1999), it is “a process of creating a favourable public opinion for an organization,

institution, individuals, commodities or intangible things such as names, etc, so that people who have something to do with them may perceive them in a good way”.

The modified and expanded version of the British Institute of Public Relations sees Public Relations as that management function that reconciles public opinion and interests with corporate interest and policies for their mutual understanding, mutual acceptance and mutual benefits (Nwosu, 1992). The definition known as “the Mexican Statement” according to Oluwasina (2012) says that PR is “the art and social science of analyzing trends, predicting their consequences, counseling organization leaders and implementing planned programmes of action which will serve both the organizations and the public interest.” An American Public Relations expert, Rex Harlow defined PR as “a distinctive management function which helps to establish and maintain mutual lines of communication, acceptance and cooperation between an organisation and its publics. Whatever view one holds with regard to what PR means to him, it is important to note that the attitude of the key publics to any organization is shaped largely by the attitudes of the organization towards them. Therefore, if the organization is to win the goodwill and support of these publics upon whom it depends for success and survival, then what it does matters as much as what it says. This must be why PR is a two-way activity – listening to what the public thinks, as well as projecting the organisation’s messages.

Publicity: Publicity, according to Nwosu (2001) is “the planned and systematic process of making something (e.g. person, company, product, group or idea) publicly known.” He also added that it is any message about an organisation or its products that is communicated through the mass media but is not paid for by the organisation or any of its agents” (Nwosu, 2001). The major factor or characteristic that distinguished this promotion tool from advertising is the non-payment for its messages. An organization can achieve successful publicity for itself and the products by writing and distributing news worthy press releases, corporate articles or features using firms and photographs in showcasing the organization and its product, sponsoring events that will attract the attention of the media.

Event Marketing: Events marketing is a specialized area in modern marketing communications management defined as “marketing or sponsorship of special and popular newsworthy events that can attract the attention of the media.” This however is adjudged the best way of promoting organizations and its products, goodwill and acceptance. The events that fall under this category include:

- (i) Sporting Events
- (ii) Product Launches
- (iii) Arts and Cultural Carnivals
- (iv) Educational Scholarships endowments, seminars
- (v) Award ceremonies,
- (vi) Special anniversary celebrations
- (vii) Special convocation ceremonies, music and concert shows, etc. (Black, 1989)

Sales Promotion: The American Marketing Association (AMA) (1995) defined Sales Promotion as “those marketing activities other than personal selling, advertising, and publicity that stimulate customer purchasing and dealer effectiveness, such as displays, shows and exhibitions, demonstrations and various non recurrent selling efforts not in the ordinary routine. Sales promotion is also said to mean marketing activities usually specific to a direct response from consumers or marketing intermediaries, through the offer of additional benefits. Nwosu (2001) defined it as “a direct inducement which offers an extra value or incentive for the product to the sales force, distributors, ultimate consumers”. “Sales promotion supplements advertising and personal selling efforts which explains why it is hardly used alone as a promotools, instead it is properly integrated into and coordinated with the company’s overall advertising, personal selling, public relations and other marketing communication plans” (Nwosu, 1996). Another reason for not using it alone is because while

advertising and personal selling effort both have long term tenures and effects, sales promotion is short termed and has short-lasting effects

“**Sales promotion** stimulates customer purchasing with such extra values or incentives like lotteries, exhibitions, premium and gifts, sampling, trade shows, demonstrations, couponing, rebates, low interest financing, entertainments, tie-ins, etc, which are combined with heavy advertising and publicity” (Nwosu, 2001).

Sales promotion achieves the following:

- (i) supplements advertising and personal selling efforts.
- (ii) builds trial among non-users and attracts switchers away from competitors.
- (iii) dramatises product offers and boosts sagging sales.
- (iv) stimulates off-season buying and fights the promotional efforts of competing goods or firms.
- (v) helps to win customers for new products and creates interests among customers for old products.
- (vi) cushions the effects of price increase.
- (vii) creates attention gaining information that leads the customer to the product.

Sales promotions can come in the following forms:

Price-based value increasing promotions:

- Discount pricing and sales
- Money-off coupons
- Refunds
- Improved payment terms

Product-based value increasing promotions:

- Product samples
- Multipacks and multibuys
- Improved product quality.
- Increased product quantity.

Tangible value adding promotions:

- Valued packaging
- Premiums
- Gift coupons

Opportunity-based value adding promotions:

- Competitions
- Promotional Information
- Guarantees
- Product buyback and exchange schemes
- Clubs

Personal Selling: Nwosu (2001) defined personal selling as “person-to-person communication in which the receiver provides immediate feedback to the source’s message through words, gestures, expressions, and the likes” (Kotler, 1993) defined it as “oral presentation in a conversation with one or more prospective purchaser(s) for the purpose of making sales”. Many scholars however refer to sales force as the “eye and ears of the company”, and for good reasons, “the front line of revenue generation for the organization.” Personal selling is most appropriate where the unit of sale is large enough to support the cost of the contact. It is also said to be most ideal where the product benefits have to be carefully matched to the customer’s desire. Personal selling is adjudged the most expensive among all the marketing communication tools, and slow in total outreach

(market coverage), yet very inevitable in situations where the product is rather heavy, expensive and complex, like in the case of industrial products, requiring some technical and detailed explanations or demonstrations. The role of personal selling in the performance of the marketing functions cannot be over emphasized. It is the order of the day in most exchange situations. This is because it is unlikely that any sales can be made without first establishing a personal contact. In personal selling situations, the task of the salesperson is to provide prospective buyers with information and other benefits, motivating and persuading them to make buying decisions in favour of the product or service.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This chapter discusses the methods adopted in carrying out this research work. It also discusses in details, the structural procedures/approaches for gathering the information for this work. The chapter contains the sources of data generation, methods of investigation, instruments of data collection, population of the study, sample size, sampling techniques, validity and reliability of research instrument, and methods of data presentation and analysis.

Research Design

The survey method of research design was adopted for this work due to the large population of the study area. Survey research requires eliciting information from the people/respondents using either verbal (oral interviews) or written questions (questionnaire). It focuses on people, the vital facts of people and their beliefs, opinions, attitudes, emotions, and behaviour.

Primary Data

Primary data for this work was obtained from survey using both direct contacts and telephone interviews. Questionnaire was also distributed to individuals and members of some organizations directly affected by HIV/AIDS, and those directly involved in the fight against the scourge in the state. A well-structured questionnaire which contains thirty one (31) questions, comprising of some multiple choice and “Yes-or-No” question types, was administered to all the relevant groups.

Instrument for Data Collection and Method of Investigation

The study made use of face-to-face/ telephone interviews and questionnaire administration. The face-to-face interviews were conducted among the selected key respondents who are more knowledgeable in the field. This provides the researcher the opportunity to obtain direct physiological response from the respondents on the issues raised with them, and to compliment the data generated from the questionnaire.

Population of the Study

The population for the study comprised of the key relevant publics of the study which include the groups identified as the stakeholders who are directly or indirectly involved in the HIV/AIDS intervention programmes in the state. They are as follows:

- Network of People with HIV/AIDS of Nigeria (NEPWHAN).
- ENSACA Staff and Board Members
- Hospital staff comprising of the Doctors, Nurses, Counsellors and Laboratory Technicians.
- Foreign Partner Agencies
- Local Non-Governmental Organisations
- Media Workers (Radio and Television)
- Private Sector Organisations
- Faith Based Organisations

Table 1: Population Distribution

Organisations	No. of Staff
Network of People With HIV/AIDS of Nigeria (NEPWHAN)	38
Enugu State Action Committee on AIDS (ENSACA) Staff	22
Hospital Staff (Parklane Specialist Hospital, Enugu): (Doctors, Nurses, Counsellors & Lab. Technicians)	21
Representatives/Staff of Foreign Partner/Donor Agencies (HIV & AIDS Comprehensive Care initiative (URC HACCI) Nigeria	15
Local Non-Governmental Organisations: (Society for Family Health)	20
Media Workers: (Radio and Television) FRCN, Enugu and NTA Enugu.	18
Private Sector Organisations: (Senior Staff of EMENITE Plc, Emene, Enugu)	15
Faith Based Organisations: (Emmanuel Anglican Church, Achara Layout, Enugu)	16
TOTAL	165

Source: Researcher’s Field Work, 2015.

Pilot Survey

The researcher distributed some copies of questionnaire to a small population for pilot study in order to know the response of the respondents. Seven (7) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to each of the eight (8) organizations selected for sampling, giving a total of fifty six (56) copies. When they were filled and returned, it was re-administered to the respondents after an interval of two (2) weeks. Again, they were filled and returned, this time, with a slight difference. The positive response is consistent enough. The purpose of the pilot survey, however, is to establish the reliability of the research instrument.

Table 2 Response Rate on Pilot Survey

Organisations	1 st Test Result (X)	2 nd Test Result (Y)	XY	X ²	Y ²
1	7	7	49	49	49
2	4	6	24	16	36
3	7	7	49	49	49
4	4	6	24	16	36
5	6	6	36	36	36
6	5	5	25	25	25
7	4	6	24	16	36
8	5	5	25	25	25
Total	42	48	256	232	292

Source: Researcher’s Fieldwork, 2015.

Formula:
$$r = \frac{n\sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2][n\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

Thus:
$$r = \frac{56(256) - (42)(48)}{\sqrt{[56(232) - (42)^2][56(292) - (48)^2]}}$$

$$r = \frac{14336 - 2016}{\sqrt{(12992 - 1764)(16352 - 2304)}}$$

$$r = \frac{12320}{\sqrt{(11228)(14048)}}$$

$$r = \frac{12320}{\sqrt{157730944}}$$

$$r = \frac{12320}{(12559.09806)}$$

$$r = 0.9809622$$

Sample Size Determination

In determining the sample size, the judgmental sampling process was used to select the organizations that form the basis of this study. The simple random sampling was adopted in selecting the staff respondents, while the stratified sampling method was used in selecting the population sample from the different organizations used in the study.

The sample size was determined using Yamane formula at 0.05 level of significance, while the stratified sample was used to select the sub groups.

Therefore, using Yamane's formula (1967):

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \quad (\text{equation 1})$$

Where n = sample size
 N = total population
 1 = constant
 e = error margin

For stratified sample formula:

$$n_1 = n \left(\frac{N_1}{N} \right) \quad (\text{equation 2})$$

Where n_1 = sample size strata 1
 n = sample size of N_1
 N_1 = population of strata 1
 N = total population

Substituting as in equation 1:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{165}{1 + 165(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{165}{1 + 165(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{165}{1 + 0.4125}$$

$$n = \frac{165}{1.4125}$$

$$n = 117$$

Working for the strata, to stratify the above sample size (to determine the number of copies of questionnaire to be distributed in each of the organization), we substitute in equation 2 thus:

1. **Network of People with HIV/AIDS:**

$$n_1 = \frac{n(N_1)}{N}$$

$$= \frac{117(38)}{165} = 27$$

2. **Staff of ENSACA:**

$$= \frac{117(22)}{165} = 15$$

3. **Staff of Parklane Specialist Hospital, Enugu**

$$= \frac{117(21)}{165} = 15$$

4. **Representatives/Staff of Foreign Partners**

$$= \frac{117(15)}{165} = 11$$

5. **Local NGOs (Society for Family Health)**

$$= \frac{117(20)}{165} = 14$$

6. **Staff of FRCN and NTA Enugu**

$$= \frac{117(18)}{165} = 13$$

7. **Senior Staff of Emenite PLC, Emene, Enugu**

$$= \frac{117(15)}{165} = 11$$

8. **Pastors and PCC Committee members of Emmanuel Anglican Church, Achara Layout, Enugu**

$$= \frac{117(16)}{165} = 11$$

Table 3: Break down of the Sample Size

Organisations	Population	Sample
Network of People with HIV/AIDS (NEPWHAN)	38	27
Staff of ENSACA	22	15
Staff of Parklane Specialist Hospital, Enugu	21	15
Staff of Foreign Partners (URC-HACCI Nigeria)	15	11
Local NGOs (Society for Family Health)	20	14
Staff of FRCN and NTA Enugu	18	13
Senior Staff of EMENITE PLC, Enugu	15	11
Pastors and PCC members of Emmanuel Anglican Church, Achara Layout, Enugu	16	11
Total	165	117

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

Note: After determining the sample size of the study, with due consultations, the researcher thought it more appropriate to sample the entire population of 165 respondents instead, considering the fact that the said population was relatively not too large to deal with. To justify this action, he endeavoured to ensure that every questionnaire distributed was carefully filled and returned by the respondents.

Sampling Techniques

In this study, probability stratified sampling technique was adopted while simple random sampling technique was applied in the administration of the questionnaire to the different groups identified above as the population of the study.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The questionnaire was vetted by the researcher's supervisor and other marketing experts in IMT and ESUT respectively based on face value in terms of relevance of subject matter, objective of the study, coverage of content areas, language usage and clarity of purpose. In testing the validity and reliability of the test instrument, Cronbach's Alpha was used. An Alpha of 0.930 and inter-item (standard) coefficient of 0.973 were obtained. These being greater than 0.7 indicate that the reliability of test instrument is very strong.

Method of Data Presentation and Analysis

Tables, mean and percentages were used to summarize the data gathered for clarity and comprehension, while the four (4) hypotheses were tested using the Correlation Statistical Tool.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

HYPOTHESES

Four hypotheses were formulated and tested in this study using correlation statistical tools.

Hypothesis 1

1. There is no significant relationship between increased television messages and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State.

Determination of the Relationship between increased Television messages and Awareness Creation Campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State

Table 4 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
There is no Significant Relationship Between increased TV messages and Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State	2.9266	.72995	354
	3.0367	.97056	354

Table 4 above shows the descriptive statistics of the effect of television in creating awareness campaign against HIV/AIDS with the mean response of 2.9266 and standard deviation of 0.72995 for television messages and a mean response of 3.0367 and standard deviation of 0.97056 for awareness. By careful observation of standard deviation value, it can be said that there is about the same variability of data point amongst the dependent and independent variables. This implies that awareness of HIV/AIDS is directly influenced by television messages.

Table 5 Correlations

		There is no Significant Relationship Between increased TV messages and Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu state	Reduction
There is no Significant Relationship Between increased TV messages and Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu state	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N		.756** .000 354
Awareness	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.756** .000 354	1 354

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5 above shows Pearson correlation coefficient for television messages and awareness campaign against HIV/AIDS. The correlation shows 0.756. This value indicates that correlation coefficient is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there is a relationship between television messages and HIV/AIDS awareness ($r = 0.756$). The computed correlation coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 363 degree of freedom (df n-2) at alpha level for a two tailed test ($r = 0.756, p < .05$). We reject the null hypothesis.

Hypothesis 2:

2. There is no significant relationship between increased radio messages and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State.

Determination of the Relationship between increased Radio messages and Awareness Creation Campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State

Table 6 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
There is no Significant Relationship Between increased Radio messages and Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu state	2.9605	.92410	354
Awareness	3.0282	.91217	354

The table above shows the descriptive statistics of the effect of radio in creating awareness campaign against HIV/AIDS, with the mean response of 2.9605 and standard deviation of 0.92410 for radio and a mean response of 3.0282 and standard deviation of 0.91217 for awareness. By careful observation of standard deviation value, it can be said that there is about the same variability of data point amongst the dependent and independent variables. This implies that awareness of HIV/AIDS is directly influenced by radio messages.

Table 7 Correlations

		There is no Significant Relationship Between increased Radio messages and Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu state	Reduction
There is no Significant Relationship Between increased Radio messages and Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu state	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N		.700** .000 354
Awareness	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.700** .000 354	1 354

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 7 above shows Pearson correlation coefficient for radio messages and awareness campaign against HIV/AIDS. The correlation shows 0.700. This value indicates that correlation coefficient is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there is a relationship between radio messages and HIV/AIDS awareness ($r = 0.700$). The computed correlation coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 363 degree of freedom (df n-2) at alpha level for a two tailed test ($r = 0.700, p < .05$). We reject the null hypothesis.

Hypothesis 3

3. There is no significant relationship between increased Newspaper messages and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State.

Determination of the Relationship between increased Newspaper messages and Awareness Creation Campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State

Table 8 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
There is no Significant Relationship Between increased Newspaper messages and Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State	2.2345	1.00641	354
State	2.1186	1.00285	354

Table 8 above shows the descriptive statistics of the effect of newspaper messages in creating awareness campaign against HIV/AIDS, with the mean response of 2.2345 and standard deviation of 1.00641 for newspapers and a mean response of 2.1186 and standard deviation of 1.00285 for awareness. By careful observation of standard deviation value, it can be said that there is about the same variability of data point amongst the dependent and independent variables. This implies that awareness of HIV/AIDS is directly influenced by newspaper messages.

Table 9 Correlations

		There is no Significant Relationship Between increased Newspaper messages and Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State	Reduction
There is no Significant Relationship Between increased Newspaper messages and Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State	Pearson Correlation		.789**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	354	354
Awareness	Pearson Correlation	.789**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	354	354

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 9 above shows Pearson correlation coefficient for newspaper messages and awareness campaign against HIV/AIDS. The correlation shows 0.789. This value indicates that correlation coefficient is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there is a relationship between newspaper messages and HIV/AIDS awareness ($r = 0.789$). The computed correlation coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 363 degree of freedom (df $n-2$) at alpha level for a two tailed test ($r = 0.789, p < .05$). Therefore we reject the null hypothesis.

Hypothesis 4

- There is no significant relationship between increased use of the word-of-mouth and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State.

Determination of the Relationship between increased use of the Word-of-Mouth and Awareness Creation Campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State

Table 10 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
There is no Significant Relationship Between increased use of the Word-of-Mouth and Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State	1.8842	.99325	354
	1.8672	.82586	354

Table 10 above shows the descriptive statistics of the effect of the word-of-mouth in creating awareness campaign against HIV/AIDS, with the mean response of 1.8842 and standard deviation of 0.99325 for the word- of -mouth and a mean response of 1.8672 and standard deviation of 0.82586 for awareness. By careful observation of standard deviation value, it can be said that there is about the same variability of data point amongst the dependent and independent variables. This implies that awareness of HIV/AIDS is directly influenced by word-of-mouth messages.

Table 11 Correlations

		There is no Significant Relationship Between increased use of the Word-of-Mouth and Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu state	Reduction
There is no Significant Relationship Between increased use of the Word-of-Mouth and Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State	Pearson Correlation		.872**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	354	354
Awareness	Pearson Correlation	.872**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	354	354

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 11 above shows Pearson correlation coefficient for word-of-mouth and awareness campaign against HIV/AIDS. The correlation shows 0.872. This value indicates that correlation coefficient is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there is a relationship between the word-of-mouth and HIV/AIDS awareness ($r = 0.872$). The computed correlation coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 363 degree of freedom (df n-2) at alpha level for a two tailed test ($r = 0.872, p < .05$). We reject the null hypothesis.

Summary of the Findings

After a critical statistical analysis and testing of the data generated for this study, the following findings were obtained:

Results of the Tested Hypothesis:

- (i) Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in Enugu State is significantly influenced by the increased television messages.

(ii) The relationship between increased radio messages and awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state was significant.

(i) Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state is significantly influenced by increased use of newspapers.

(ii) The increased word-of-mouth had a significant effect on awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS in the state.

Conclusion

The application and injection of integrated marketing communications in abating the scourge of HIV/AIDS in Enugu State had been meager.

Recommendations

Based on the above findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Adequate Application of the appropriate Marketing Communication Tools

The appropriate marketing communication tools such as television, radio, newspapers, and the word-of-mouth, should be adequately applied in creating the desired awareness campaigns against HIV/AIDS in the state.

(i) Television and Radio

(a) In packaging such messages special considerations should be given to some known interactive (audience participatory) programmes like the phone-in programmes, press conferences/briefings, special interviews, discussion forums, dramas, debates, exhibitions, etc, where opportunities are created for people to either make contributions or ask questions on relevant areas of doubts and confusions for necessary clarifications. Messages delivered in these forms are often understood better, assimilated faster and retained longer in the minds of the audience.

All other forms of result oriented marketing communication strategies must also be invoked to ensure that the desired results are achieved in these awareness campaigns. These include the use of press releases, news commentaries, editorials, documentaries, features, articles, films, suggestion boxes, etc.

(b) Television and Radio stations within and around the state should be encouraged to boost/enhance their reception/transmission capacities so that even those residing in the rural communities of the state can have easy and free access to their programmes which includes HIV/AIDS messages.

(c) The concerned authorities should endeavour to extend the public power supply (electricity) to our rural communities, as well as improving on the power generating capacity in the country generally. Rehabilitation of Oji-River Power Station, which is capable of serving the entire South East States, can solve this problem permanently.

(d) The state and Local Government Authorities should establish Free Television Viewing Centres (FTVCs), especially in various rural communities of the state so that those who are not privileged to have such gargets can have access to current news and other educative programmes.

(e) Governments should establish different poverty reduction and eradication initiatives that will help ease the economic tension in the state and Nigeria generally. See p.

(ii) Word-of-Mouth

Also recommended for possible adoption is a proper integration and active involvement of some concerned Civil Society Organisations, like the Network of People with HIV/AIDS in Nigeria (NEPWHAN), otherwise called the HIV/AIDS support groups, in all the intervention programmes in the state. They live with this virus and as such, no one else can possibly preach the message better than they can. They are capable and willing to render help even as volunteers, especially on advocacy capacity as this will, no doubt, create more impact in the psyche of the people and subsequently translate into adopting the new behavior changes.

Film makers and the musicians (highlife, hip-up, gospel, etc) should be motivated to use their talents in sensitizing the public on HIV/AIDS issues through their films and songs. The introduction of these three special groups of persons (the Gate-Keepers, the HIV/AIDS support groups and the Performing Artists) in delivering this patriotic mandate at this critical period of this fight is not only strategic but tactical and very timely too. The gate-keepers include the traditional institutions, the town union executives, age grades, the women organizations through their various organs like the August Meetings, the Umuada meetings, music groups, etc, the religious leaders, and schools authorities, etc. Messages channeled through these medium and sufficiently reinforced with the necessary radio/television jingles and advertisements will surely guarantee sufficient coverage.

(iii) Newspapers and Magazines

(a) Establishment of weekly magazines that will carry HIV/AIDS messages at all the Local Government Area headquarters is recommended to satisfy especially, the desires of the rural dwellers who always felt starved of necessary information.

Apart from the HIV/AIDS messages, such magazine should carry other interesting issues like: Health tips, diet options, alternative medication, food preservation methods, pictures of some important personalities and events, current affairs, some exotic places, and other newsworthy social issues capable of attracting and holding attentions.

- Awareness creation campaign against HIV/AIDS should be extended to our schools by way of integrating it into the school curriculum up to tertiary institutions.
- Re-introduction of civic education and moral instructions to inculcate good morals among the youths should also be considered for possible adoption in our school system.

2. The Appropriate Language(s) for the Messages

Igbo, Pigeon and English Languages are recommended as the most appropriate languages for the awareness creation in the state. Above all, most of the radio and television programmes, should be presented in the morning and evening periods when the target population whom the messages are designed for would be around and disposed to listen to the messages and/or participate in such programmes.

3. Reduction on Stigma and Discrimination of PLWHA

Messages should be designed to promote the rights of PLWHA and reduce stigma and discrimination against them by continuously dispelling the myths that HIV is an instant death sentence and that every positive person is a walking corpse.

4. Addressing the Misconceptions on the Existence of HIV/AIDS

A real-life situation-based communication method like **paying visits** to a couple of full-blown AIDS patients by youths organizations and senior secondary school students can create the best effects and help to communicate fears and conviction especially among those who are still in doubt about the existence of AIDS. Seeing, they say, is believing. Also very necessary is organizing seminars in schools using the PLWHA through their support groups as resource persons to provide the first-hand information that the virus is real and lives on. Such confessions from those living with the virus themselves can have far-reaching impact on the target audience, especially the curious ones.

5. Aggressive Promotion of Abstinence and Condom Use

Having identified sex as the most common mode of transmitting and spreading the AIDS virus, abstinence and condom use, especially among the most vulnerable groups (youths) must always be emphasized in all the HIV/AIDS messages in the state. Efforts should be made therefore, to convince the religious leaders to adopt the use of condom as a wise and viable alternative especially where abstinence is unachievable, as against their earlier notion and claims that it promotes promiscuity among the youths instead.

6. **Proper Funding and Coordination of the Programme in the State**

- (i) Logistics are as vital to the success of any project as appropriate tools. Therefore, increased funding of the sector by the government and more participation of the local Non-governmental Organisations (NGOs) in the state HIV/AIDS intervention project are advocated for and encouraged.
- (iii) Proper articulation and coordination of all the assistance provided by the donor/partner agencies in the state (centralizing the funding approach), is also recommended. Such assistances are in the form of financial, material and technical aids.
- (iv) (iii) The coordinating agencies in the state should endeavour to put in place the necessary mechanisms to monitor and evaluate the progress of all the programmes initiated in the state in order to identify the problems encountered by the programme participants so that areas of needs will be addressed.

7. **Improvements on Policy Related Issues**

All the identified policy related issues that confront the fight against HIV/AIDS in Nigeria generally and Enugu State in particular, should be well addressed. This can be initiated by setting aside all the unnecessary bureaucratic bottlenecks that restrict the formulations and implementation process of these policies. Such issues include:

- (i) Unnecessary delays in enacting such legislations
- (ii) Lack of legal backings for enforcement of the policies
- (iii) Legal restrictions and policy inconsistencies
- (iv) Faith based, Education and media related restrictions.
- (v) Inadequate funding of the sector
- (vi) Labour and work-place policies
- (vii) Inadequate involvement of stakeholders in the policy formulation and implementations, etc.

8. **Establishment of Poverty Alleviation Programmes in the State**

Having identified poverty and unemployment as major threats to sustainable development and as the key factors in the spread of HIV/AIDS in the state, the state government should increase its efforts in the area of economic empowerment through its State poverty Reduction Strategy Programme, especially to the most-at-risk population (women and youths). Creating income-generating activities for the low-income women in the state and designing rehabilitation programmes for those in the prostitution business, are very crucial in preventing HIV/AIDS and in mitigating its impacts, especially now that many of them have already expressed genuine willingness to quit the ugly business if provided with alternative means of livelihood. So, HIV/AIDS interventions should always be linked to poverty alleviation programmes.

9. **Discouragement of Socio-Cultural Practices that Promote the Spread of HIV/AIDS in the State**

The identified obnoxious sex related violence and gender based harmful traditional socio-cultural practices that tend to fuel the epidemic and expose people to HIV/AIDS infections must be outrightly condemned and discouraged in the state. Such practices include: Rape, Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) otherwise called Female circumcision, widowhood practice/inheritance, wife sharing or transfer of spouses (sexual hospitality), forced early marriages, traumatic puberty initiative rites, having sex with virgins and mad women as cure for HIV/AIDS, and as means of making quick money, etc.

10. **Provision of More Health Care Facilities (ART, VCT Centres, etc).**

ART centres should be decentralized to increase access to the drugs and to reduce the undue stress persons living with the virus go through in accessing such services in the state. Voluntary Counseling and Testing Centres, free HIV testing, ART drugs and treatment for PLWHA should be improved upon and made available and accessible in the state. It is only when people know their status that the cycle of silence and myths of misconceptions that fuel the epidemic can be broken.

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